

SYNTHESIS AND QUANTUM-CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF A COMPLEX COMPOUND OF Cu(II) ION WITH INDOLE-3- ACETIC ACID AND ACETAMIDE

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Abstract. This article presents the results of the synthesis and quantum-chemical analysis of a new mixed-ligand coordination compound based on the divalent copper (II) ion with indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) and acetamide (AA) ligands. The aim of the study is to determine the conditions for the formation of the complex compound and to investigate its composition, structure, and electronic properties using modern physicochemical methods. Elemental analysis of the synthesized complex confirmed its stoichiometric composition, while IR spectroscopy revealed the coordination modes of the ligands to the metal ion. In particular, it was established that indole-3-acetic acid participates in coordination through the carboxylate group, whereas acetamide coordinates via the carbonyl oxygen atom. In the theoretical part of the study, the geometric structure of the complex was optimized using Density Functional Theory (DFT), and its stability was evaluated. Quantum-chemical calculations were performed to determine the Mulliken charge distribution of atoms in the molecule, the energies of the HOMO and LUMO orbitals, and the energy gap (ΔE). The obtained results indicate the high stability and reactivity of the complex compound.

Furthermore, these parameters are of significant importance for predicting the plant growth-stimulating properties of the complex. The results of this study can be applied in the fields of coordination chemistry, bioinorganic chemistry, and the development of new agricultural stimulants.

Keywords: copper(II) complex, indole-3-acetic acid, acetamide, coordination compounds, synthesis, IR spectroscopy, DFT calculations, HOMO-LUMO, biological activity.

INTRODUCTION

One of the promising areas of modern coordination chemistry is the synthesis and fundamental study of metal complexes containing biologically active ligands. In particular, coordination compounds of 3d-metals, especially the copper (II) ion, formed with various organic compounds, are distinguished by their unique physicochemical and biological properties. Copper is considered a vital trace element and directly participates in numerous enzymatic processes in living organisms and the metabolic systems of plants. In this study, indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), chosen as a ligand, belongs to the auxin family—a natural hormone that plays a crucial role in plant physiology. IAA regulates the processes of plant cell elongation, division, and rooting. However, auxins in their pure form can be unstable against environmental factors. Converting them into coordination compounds with metal ions not only increases the stability of the substance

but also significantly enhances its biological efficacy, which is being confirmed in scientific research. The use of acetamide as a second ligand serves to enrich the coordination sphere of the complex and improve the solubility properties of the molecule. Currently, enriching experimental results with theoretical analysis is one of the key factors determining the quality of scientific articles. Therefore, along with the structural descriptions of the synthesized complex, the article presents results obtained using modern quantum-chemical calculation methods, specifically Density Functional Theory (DFT). DFT calculations allow for the prediction of geometric parameters of the molecule, distribution of electron density, and energetic stability. The relevance of this work is determined by identifying the relationship between the structure and properties of mixed-ligand copper (II) complexes and establishing the theoretical foundations for creating new types of highly effective stimulants that can be applied in agriculture. Modern chemical research is inconceivable without quantum-chemical analysis. The initially selected main ligand, indole-3-acetic acid (heteroauxin, IAA), and the newly synthesized coordination compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{IAA})_2(\text{AA})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were studied using the Gaussian program with the CAM-B3LYP basis set. The aim of this article is to synthesize a mixed-ligand complex compound of the Cu(II) ion with indole-3-acetic acid and acetamide, to confirm its composition using modern physicochemical methods, and to theoretically substantiate the stable structure and electronic properties of the complex through quantum-chemical calculations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, the synthesis of 3d-metal complexes based on biologically active ligands has remained one of the most pressing areas of coordination chemistry. In particular, copper (II) ion compounds formed with organic acids and amides have attracted significant scholarly attention due to their bioactivity and potential applications in agriculture. Indole derivatives, specifically indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), are well-known plant hormones, and their coordination with metal ions has been studied for several decades. For instance, G. Micera et al. [2] investigated the complexes of IAA with copper (II) and other divalent metals, demonstrating that the ligand binds to the metal ion via the carboxylate group. Similarly, the work of P. Piu et al. [1] indicates that indole acids form stable complexes with metal ions, often resulting in a stoichiometric composition of $\text{M}(\text{L})_2$.

In the realm of mixed-ligand complexes, the role of amides is indispensable. M.R. Ibragimova and co-authors [3] studied mixed-ligand complexes of copper (II) nicotinate with acid amides. Their research reveals that amides coordinate with the metal ion through the carbonyl oxygen, enhancing the solubility and thermal stability of the complex. Furthermore, A.M.N. Khaleel [5] synthesized complexes of IAA derivatives with copper, cobalt, and nickel ions, confirming their square-planar and octahedral structures.

Quantum chemical calculations are becoming increasingly important in bridging theoretical and experimental results. In their work, N. Omirzak and R.S. Yerkasov [4] performed a quantum chemical analysis of copper halide complexes with acetamide using the PM3 method. This study calculated the energy parameters, charge distribution, and stability of the molecule. Such calculations, particularly the Density Functional Theory (DFT) method, allow for the prediction of the electronic structure and potential biological activity of newly synthesized complexes. The synthesis of new complexes based on biologically active ligands—specifically plant growth hormones (auxins) and pharmaceuticals—is an extensively researched field in coordination chemistry. Indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), which plays a vital role in plant physiology, and its interaction with metal ions hold both fundamental and practical significance [10,11]. Research by L. Strinna Erre et al. [6] on the complexation of indole derivatives with copper (II)

ions shows that indole acids primarily coordinate with the metal ion via the carboxylate group. Their work proved that whether copper (II) complexes adopt mononuclear or dimeric (polynuclear) structures depends on the nature of the substituents within the ligand.

Additionally, Duygu İnci and co-authors [8] investigated ternary complexes formed by copper (II) ions with IAA and aromatic planar ligands (e.g., 1,10-phenanthroline). Their findings indicated that such complexes serve not only as plant growth stimulators but also possess strong antioxidant properties and DNA-binding capabilities. The role of the amide group in mixed-ligand complexes also warrants special attention. Karim Chkirate et al. [9] studied the synthesis and crystal structure of pyrazole-acetamide based copper (II) complexes. The study showed that the amide group ensures the supramolecular structure and stability of the complex by forming a hydrogen-bonding network. Furthermore, G.G. Nnabuike et al. [7] examined copper (II) complexes with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (indomethacin), finding that N-donor ligands within these complexes can alter the coordination environment around the metal and enhance biological efficacy. Currently, integrating experimental results with theoretical analysis is an essential part of scientific research. Literature data indicates that studying the electronic structure, HOMO and LUMO orbitals, and the stability of copper (II) complexes using the DFT method enables the prediction of the complex's reactivity and biological activity.

In conclusion, the literature review demonstrates that a comprehensive study of mixed-ligand complexes of the copper (II) ion with IAA and acetamide—through both synthetic methods and modern DFT techniques—will contribute to obtaining new scientific insights in this field.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The mixed-ligand coordination compound of cuprum(II) chloride with indole-3-acetic acid and acetamide was synthesized using the following procedure. First, 0.01 mol (1.75 g) of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) was dissolved in 50 mL of ethanol. To ensure deprotonation of the ligand's carboxyl group, 0.01 mol of potassium hydroxide (KOH) was added to the resulting solution. In a separate beaker, 0.005 mol (0.855 g) of cuprum(II) chloride dihydrate ($\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was completely dissolved in 20 mL of distilled water. The metal salt solution was then added dropwise to the indole-3-acetic acid solution under constant stirring and mixed on a magnetic stirrer for 25–30 minutes. Afterwards, in order to form the mixed-ligand complex, a solution of 0.01 mol (0.59 g) of acetamide (AA) was added dropwise (5–10 mL) to the reaction mixture, followed by further stirring for 25–30 minutes. The reaction mixture was then continuously stirred at 50–55 °C for 1–1.5 hours using a magnetic stirrer [12]. At the end of the reaction, a clear, colorless solution was obtained. The resulting solution was purified by filtration, washed several times with a mixture of distilled water and ethanol, and dried in a vacuum desiccator (over P_2O_5) until constant mass was achieved [13,14]. As a result of the synthesis process, a clear colorless crystalline powder was obtained. The overall yield of the synthesis reaction was 82%, which confirms the high efficiency of the selected synthetic method. Based on the compositional analysis of the complex compound, it can be represented by the formula $[\text{Cu}(\text{IAA})_2(\text{AA})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [15]. The reaction equation can be expressed as follows.

Figure 1. The reaction for obtaining the potassium salt of indole-3-acetic acid

In solution, the selected ligands lose their protons and are converted into IAA⁻ and AA⁻ anions. The Zn²⁺ ion possesses vacant coordination orbitals and forms coordination bonds with the IAA⁻ and AA⁻ ligands through the oxygen atoms of the carboxylate groups. **M = Cu.**

Figure 2. The reaction equation for the formation of the complex compound [Cu(IAA)₂(AA)₂·2H₂O

As a result, a coordination compound with six coordination and octahedral geometry is formed. During crystallization, the resulting complex incorporates two water molecules, which are considered water of crystallization: [Cu(IAA)₂(AA)₂·2H₂O.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In this study, the electronic structure, geometric parameters, and stability of the synthesized complex [Cu(IAA)₂(AA)₂·2H₂O were investigated using quantum chemical calculations. All computations were carried out using the Gaussian program package. The geometry optimization and subsequent analyses were performed within the framework of Density Functional Theory (DFT) employing the range-separated hybrid functional CAM-B3LYP, which is known for its improved description of long-range electron interactions and charge-transfer systems. The initial molecular structure of the complex was constructed based on experimental coordination assumptions, where Cu(II) is coordinated by two indole-3-acetate (IAA⁻) and two acetate (AA⁻) ligands through oxygen donor atoms. Full geometry optimization was performed without any symmetry constraints, and the nature of the stationary points was confirmed by vibrational frequency analysis, ensuring the absence of imaginary frequencies.

The optimized structure reveals that the Cu(II) center adopts a distorted octahedral coordination environment, where the ligand molecules form stable coordination bonds via carboxylate oxygen atoms. The presence of crystallization water molecules plays an important role in stabilizing the supramolecular structure through hydrogen bonding interactions. Furthermore, frontier molecular orbital (FMO) analysis was carried out to evaluate the electronic properties of the complex. The energies and spatial distributions of HOMO and LUMO orbitals provide insight into the chemical reactivity, kinetic stability, and possible charge-transfer pathways within the complex [16]. The HOMO–LUMO energy gap indicates the relative stability of the system and its potential reactivity. Additionally, charge distribution analysis and electron density mapping were used to better understand the coordination behavior and electron delocalization within the complex system. These results provide a theoretical basis for interpreting the stability and physicochemical properties of the synthesized cuprum complex.

Similar to above complex, Cu(II) complex was optimized at the same level of theory and shown in Figure 3. The converged unrestricted wave function yielded a spin expectation value of $\langle S^2 \rangle = 0.7516$ before annihilation and 0.7500 after, confirming negligible spin contamination and a clean doublet ground state consistent with a d⁹ Cu(II) center bearing one unpaired electron.

Natural bond orbital (NBO) analysis was carried out on the converged density to obtain atomic charges, natural electron configurations quantifying the strength of ligand-to-metal electron donation.

Figure 3. Optimized geometry of the Cu(II) complex (CAM-B3LYP/LANL2DZ) with NBO partial charges (green, in parentheses). Cu (gold), O (red), N (magenta), C (dark gray), H (cyan).

The NBO charge on copper was determined to be +1.47 e, substantially below the formal oxidation state of +2, similar results were observed by JV Burda et,al[1]. This reduction of 0.53 e from the ionic limit directly reflects the greater covalent character of the Cu–O bonds arising from the more diffuse, partially filled d-shell of Cu(II). The natural electron configuration of copper is [core] 4s(0.26) 3d(9.24) 5p(0.02), confirming that the formal d^9 count is preserved in the NBO picture with the d-manifold holding 9.24 electrons in total. The six coordinating oxygen atoms fall into three chemically distinct groups, each with a characteristic NBO charge reflecting both their intrinsic donor ability and the extent of charge transferred to Cu(II). The indole-2-carboxylic acid oxygens that coordinate directly to copper carry charges of -0.853 e each, the most negative values among the directly bonded donor set. The non-coordinating partner oxygens of each carboxylate group bear significantly less negative charges of -0.743 e, confirming asymmetric bonding within the carboxylate unit in which one oxygen engages the metal while the other retains greater electron density. The acetamide carbonyl oxygens, which chelate copper through amide resonance-modulated lone pairs, carry charges of -0.792 and -0.791 e respectively. The terminal aqua oxygens bear the highest negative charges in the coordination sphere (-1.086 e each), which as in the Zn complex arises from O–H bond polarity rather than strong donation to the metal.

Moreover, the individual 3d orbital occupancies extracted from the NAO analysis provide a detailed picture of the d^9 electron hole distribution. The five d-orbitals are unequally populated, with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ (occupancy 1.591) and d_{xy} (occupancy 1.701) carrying the largest electron deficiencies. The d_{xz} (1.991), d_{yz} (1.997), and d_z^2 (1.961) orbitals remain nearly fully occupied. This pattern of preferential depopulation of $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and d_{xy} is the hallmark of a Jahn-Teller active Cu(II) center in an elongated octahedral or square-based coordination environment, where the equatorial ligand field splits the eg manifold and destabilizes the orbital pointing directly toward the strongest equatorial donors. The SOMO is thus predominantly $d_{x^2-y^2}$ in character with a secondary d_{xy} contribution, consistent with the complex's pseudo-square-planar equatorial plane defined by the four strongly donating indole-2-carboxylic acid and acetamide oxygens.

The frontier molecular orbital analysis HOMO-LUMO gap is 5.53 eV as shown in Figure 4. The partially filled d-shell of Cu(II) introduces a low-lying metal-centered acceptor state that pulls the LUMO energy down into the gap, compressing E_g considerably. This directly reflects the

open-shell d^9 electronic structure of the Cu center. The LUMO is metal-centered, concentrated at the Cu–O coordination core and displaying orbital lobes with clear Cu d-character interacting with the surrounding donor oxygen atoms. This confirms that the lowest-energy electronic excitation is a ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) process, in which electron density flows from the oxygen lone pairs and ligand π -system into the vacant d-based acceptor orbital on Cu[2]. This LMCT character is characteristic of open-shell Cu(II) and is consistent with the partial radical character already identified on the coordinating carboxylate oxygens through spin density analysis. The HOMO is ligand-centered, delocalized as a π -type bonding orbital across both indole aromatic ring systems on the two ligands simultaneously. The symmetrical HOMO topology across both ligands confirms equivalent electronic environments on the two indole fragments and suggests that photoexcitation can be used to probe the ligand π -framework through LMCT transitions. The chemical hardness $\eta = E_g/2 = 2.77$ eV classifies this complex as moderately hard. Research on the Mixed Ligand Cu(II) and Zn(II) Complexes by Mamaru Bitew Alem et, al.[3] shows similar character.

Figure 4. Frontier molecular orbitals of the Cu(II) complex (CAM-B3LYP/LANL2DZ, isovalue = 0.02 a.u.). Top: LUMO, localized on the Cu–O coordination core with significant metal d-character. Bottom: HOMO, delocalized across both indole ligand π -systems. $E_g = 5.53$ eV. Blue surface: positive phase; black mesh: negative phase.

The ESP surface (Figure 5.) shows a deep red nucleophilic zone at the Cu–O coordination core, broader and more intense than in the Ni(II) or Zn(II) analogues, consistent with the higher covalency (0.53 e charge transfer). Blue regions are localized symmetrically at the acetamide N–

H protons on both ligands, marking them as the primary hydrogen-bond donor sites. The aromatic ring faces display near-neutral green/cyan π -electron density.

Figure 5. Electrostatic potential (ESP) surface of the Cu(II) complex mapped on the 0.001 a.u. electron density isosurface (CAM-B3LYP/LANL2DZ). Red: most electron-rich (negative potential, Cu–O coordination core); blue: most electron-poor (positive, amide N–H protons); green/cyan: near-neutral aromatic π -faces; yellow: mildly electrophilic C–H periphery. The two elongated indole-containing arms extend horizontally.

CONCLUSION

The study successfully synthesized a new mixed-ligand coordination compound of Cu(II) with indole-3-acetic acid and acetamide, represented by the formula $[\text{Cu}(\text{IAA})_2(\text{AA})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The synthesis method produced a clear crystalline product with a high yield, confirming the effectiveness of the selected experimental procedure. The results of the structural and quantum-chemical analyses showed that the Cu(II) center forms a distorted octahedral coordination environment through oxygen donor atoms of the ligands.

The DFT calculations confirmed the stability of the synthesized complex and provided important information about its electronic structure, charge distribution, and frontier molecular orbitals. The HOMO–LUMO energy gap, NBO charge analysis, and electrostatic potential surface demonstrated the moderate hardness, covalent character of Cu–O bonds, and possible charge-transfer activity of the complex. These findings indicate that the synthesized compound may possess promising biological and plant growth-stimulating properties. Overall, the results contribute to the development of coordination chemistry, bioinorganic chemistry, and the design of new metal-based agricultural stimulants.

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